

Emotional Intelligence and Communication in Digital Adult Education amid the Fifth Industrial Revolution

V. Karvouniaris, G. Samaras, A. Charalampakis
Education Management, University of Patras, Greece

Abstract

This research study examines Emotional Intelligence (EI) as a catalyst for effective communication in adult education within the framework of the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR). The aim is to explore parameters related to the measurement of EI, effective communication, Digital Emotional Intelligence (DEI), and adult educators' adaptability to the challenges posed by the 5IR. The study involved adult educators from across Greece. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, incorporating quantitative data from 195 educators using the pilot research instrument EICAEQ-5IR-CTO and qualitative data from 19 semi-structured interviews. Quantitative analysis revealed a strong correlation between EI and communication ($r = 0.861$), along with limited familiarity with the emotional dimension of technology. Qualitative findings highlighted the absence of institutionalized training and the need to develop empathy and cultural sensitivity, particularly in digital and hybrid learning environments. In conclusion, the integration of EI into educator training is proposed as a critical factor for professional success in the emerging industrial era.

Keywords: Digital Emotional Intelligence, Fifth Industrial Revolution, Emotional Intelligence, Communication, Adult Education

1 Introduction

In the era of the Fifth Industrial Revolution (5IR), rapid technological progress and socio-economic transformations are redefining the requirements of adult education. This study focuses on the role of Emotional Intelligence (EI) as a key factor in enhancing communication, adaptability,

and change management. The research emphasizes that adult education can no longer be confined to the transmission of knowledge and technical skills alone; it must also incorporate methodologies that foster emotional and social competence. The ability to recognize, understand, and manage emotions is shown to be critical for both learners and educators, as it facilitates the cre-

ation of a productive learning environment. Furthermore, the study explores the contribution of digital technologies to the development of EI, as well as the challenges emerging from the interaction between human and technological factors. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining quantitative and qualitative data from a diverse sample of adult educators across Greece, in order to provide a comprehensive analysis of the topic. The results suggest that the integration of EI into modern adult education practices is not only a necessity but also a strategic advantage for addressing the dynamic demands of our time. The research addresses the following questions:

- Q1:** How does EI influence the effectiveness of communication in adult education?
- Q2:** How can digital platforms and technologies support the development of EI in adult education?
- Q3:** What are the challenges and opportunities for integrating EI into adult education in the age of the 5IR?
- Q4:** How can emerging technologies of the 5IR enhance—or hinder—Emotional Intelligence?

2 The Impact of Communication, EI, and the 5IR on Adult Education

Emotional Intelligence defined as the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own emotions as well as those of others (Salovey & Mayer, 1990) [SM90], is

considered a fundamental factor for success in both personal and professional domains (Goleman, 1998) [Gol98]. In the educational context, EI is closely linked to the quality of interpersonal relationships, pedagogical effectiveness, and the creation of a positive learning environment (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009) [JG09]. Its core dimensions—self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills (Coleman, 1994) [Col94]—empower learners to cope with challenges, manage stress more effectively, and remain focused on their learning goals (Bar-On, 2006) [BO06]. Communication plays a decisive role in the learning process, interaction, and instructional effectiveness. Adult learners bring with them preformed experiences, knowledge, and values that shape how they absorb new information (Knowles et al., 2014) [KHIS14], and they seek active participation and autonomy in the learning experience (Merriam & Bierema, 2018) [MB18]. Transformative learning (Mezirow, 2000) [Mez00] requires bidirectional communication, reflection, and the renegotiation of experiences through dialogue (Taylor & Cranton, 2013) [TC13]. According to Vygotsky's theory (1978), knowledge is constructed socially through interaction, with the educator acting as a mediator and peer relationships serving as channels of learning (Lantolf & Thorne, 2006) [LT06]. Effective communication involves both verbal and non-verbal components, active listening, empathy, feedback, and emotional regulation (Brookfield, 2017) [Bro17]. Educators with high EI are better equipped to facilitate communication, reduce defensive-

Conceptual Map: EI - Communication - DEI/5IR Technologies

Figure 1: Relationship of Variables EI, Communication and 5IR Technologies

ness, foster collaboration, and build trust (Brackett et al., 2011) [BRS11], thereby significantly enhancing interpersonal dynamics and learning outcomes (Jordan & Troth, 2004) [JT04]. Although still under academic debate (Xu et al., 2018 ; Schwab, 2024) [XDK18] [Sch24], the 5IR is widely considered to be underway, progressing exponentially and driving profound socio-economic transformations (Ayinde et al., 2025) [AAA25]. It promotes a human-centric approach to technology, emphasizing the coexistence of human and artificial intelligence (AI) (Noble et al., 2022) [NMGP22]. As a living and evolving domain intrinsically linked to technological progress, education is undergoing radical transformation (Kassim, 2023) [Kas23]. In contrast to the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which prioritized automation, the 5IR highlights the importance of EI, critical thinking, and social sensitivity as essential elements for sustainability and societal

well-being (Panagiotopoulos & Karanikola, 2018) [PK18]. Contemporary pedagogical approaches focus on 21st-century skills, employing tools such as personalized and adaptive learning, project-based learning, digital inclusion, and lifelong professional development (Kennedy & Sundberg, 2020 ; European Commission, 2021) [KS20] [Com21]. Within this evolving context, adult education is being fundamentally reshaped. The adult educator co-constructs the learning experience, cultivates digital literacy and 21st-century competencies, and utilizes modern tools and innovative methodologies (Cam & Ballantine, 2025) [CB25]. Despite the opportunities presented, the 5IR also introduces significant challenges, such as the digital divide and the issue of "time poverty" among adults. Future research should focus on the development of flexible pedagogical models that integrate technological innovation with the enhancement of emotional and social intelligence.

3 Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods research design, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques. The methodological rationale was grounded in the need to explore not only the overall trends but also the personal experiences of adult educators regarding EI and effective communication within the context of the 5IR. A snowball sampling strategy was adopted on purpose, involving adult educators from diverse specialties across Greece. Participants were selected based on their professional experience in adult education and their engagement with emerging technologies. Regarding ethical considerations, participants' anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout the research process.

4 Research Instrument

The research instrument, EICAEQ-5IR-CTO (Emotional Intelligence and Communication in Adult Education Questionnaire – 5th Industrial Revolution – Communication, Technology, Organisation), was developed by our research team to investigate four key competencies of adult educators: (a) EI, (b) Effective Communication, (c) Digital Emotional Intelligence, and (d) Critical Adaptation to the human-centered principles of the 5IR. The internal consistency of the instrument was found to be exceptionally high (Cronbach's $\alpha = .949$ for the full set of items), with each individual construct also demonstrating very satisfac-

tory reliability indices. The development of the tool was based on a convergent mixed-methods research design, and its documentation includes robust evidence of psychometric validity and reliability. It was deployed in a pilot format, and a detailed methodological publication is forthcoming.

5 Quantitative Research

Data collection was conducted using the pilot standardized EICAEQ-5IR-CTO questionnaire, which comprised 84 statements rated on a five-point Likert scale. The questionnaire was distributed online between April 5 and May 10, 2025. A total of 204 participants responded, of which 9 were excluded based on control questions. The final sample consisted of 195 adult educators from various non-formal education settings. Data analysis was performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics software. Initial checks included descriptive statistical analysis and tests for normality of distributions, employing skewness and kurtosis indices as well as the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Depending on the data distribution, both parametric and non-parametric tests were applied. Group differences were examined based on demographic and educational variables, providing a comprehensive exploration of the research questions. To assess the instrument's behavior with respect to outliers, univariate z-score analysis and multivariate analysis using Mahalanobis distance were conducted.

6 Qualitative Research

The qualitative research aimed to gain an in-depth understanding of adult educators' experiences, attitudes, and perceptions related to the study's focus. The choice of a qualitative method was grounded in the need for an interpretative approach to complex social phenomena, complementing the statistical exploration of the quantitative component. The data collection instrument was a semi-structured interview protocol comprising 12 demographic questions and 19 open-ended, short-answer questions, organized into six thematic axes. The protocol was designed by our research team with a focus on the theoretical framework of the study, aiming to elicit rich descriptive and conceptual material. A total of 19 individual interviews were conducted with adult educators from diverse specialties, working across various non-formal education settings. Participants were selected based on criteria including experience in adult education, familiarity with new technologies, and willingness to engage in reflective practice. Qualitative data analysis was performed using the thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2006) [BC06].

7 Quantitative Findings

7.1 Sample

The sample of the quantitative study consisted of 195 participants. Examining the demographic characteristics of the sample, it was observed that 59.5 % of participants were female (n = 116). 43.6% were between

40-49 years old (n = 85), 41.5% were over 50 years old (n = 81), and 14.9% were under 39 years old (n = 29). Regarding educational qualifications, 72.8% (n = 142) held a postgraduate degree, 14.9% a bachelor's degree (n = 29), and 12.3% a doctoral degree (n = 24). 65.1% (n = 127) had attended seminars or training in adult education, 14.9% (n = 29) had completed postgraduate studies, while 20% (n = 39) had no related training. Certified trainers accounted for 48.7% of the sample (n = 95). Regarding work experience, 30.8% had 1-2 years, 23.6% had 3-5 years, 16.9% had 6-9 years, and 28.7% had over 10 years of experience. Regarding workplace diversity, 36.4% (n = 71) reported having worked in two or more institutions; 17.% in Vocational Training Institutes, 15.9% in Second Chance Schools, 13.3% in Vocational Training Centers, and the same percentage in other institutions. Only 3.6% reported working in Evening General or Vocational High Schools. Regarding digital skills, 75.4% (n = 147) reported having received training in New Technologies. Daily use of technological tools was reported by 61.0% (n = 119), weekly use by 28.2%, and 10.8% used them rarely. Regarding preferred educational models, 62.1% preferred face-to-face education, 25.6% hybrid models, and 12.3% distance learning. Concerning training on 5IR technologies, 27.7% had received related education, 21.5% partial education, and 50.8% none. Finally, with respect to EI, 30.8% had received some form of training or specialization in this area, whereas 69.2% had no relevant training.

Figure 2: Mean EI Subscale Score by Age Group

	EI	SA	SR	EM	MO	CO	DEI	SIR	Abbreviation	Full Term
EI	1.00	0.80	0.81	0.80	0.86	0.86	0.41	0.45	EI	Emotional Intelligence
SA	0.80	1.00	0.41	0.55	0.54	0.61	0.27	0.39	SA	Self-Awareness
SR	0.81	0.41	1.00	0.60	0.72	0.74	0.36	0.34	SR	Self-Regulation
EM	0.80	0.55	0.60	1.00	0.56	0.65	0.41	0.40	EM	Empathy
MO	0.86	0.54	0.72	0.56	1.00	0.82	0.32	0.34	MO	Motivation
CO	0.86	0.61	0.74	0.65	0.82	1.00	0.42	0.41	CO	Communication
DEI	0.41	0.27	0.36	0.41	0.32	0.42	1.00	0.70	DEI	Digital Emotional Intelligence
SIR	0.45	0.39	0.34	0.40	0.34	0.41	0.70	1.00	SIR	Fifth Industrial Revolution

Table 1: Correlations between subscales

7.2 Quantitative Research Results – Descriptive Statistics

The overall score for the “EI” dimension, which comprises the four subscales (Self-awareness, Self-regulation, Empathy, and Motivation), averaged 3.95 with a standard deviation of 0.30. This result indicates that trainers positively self-assess their emotional skills within the context of adult education. A high score was ob-

served in the “Motivation” subscale ($M = 4.37$), indicating a strong intrinsic motivation towards communication and engagement in the learning process. This was followed by “Self-regulation” ($M = 4.14$) and “Communication” ($M = 4.07$), reflecting a positive self-perception regarding emotion management and interpersonal interaction. Lower scores were reported for the “Self-awareness” ($M = 3.67$) and “Empathy” ($M = 3.66$) subscales, indicating potential challenges in recognizing internal states and un-

derstanding the emotions of others. The range of scores, spanning from 1.17 to 5.00, highlights variability among participants. The internal consistency reliability for the entire instrument was very high, with a $\alpha = 0.938$, indicating excellent coherence of responses. Statistical analyses revealed significant correlations for the Communication subscale with the level of training in adult education ($p = 0.004$), possession of trainer certification ($p = 0.011$), and educational attainment ($p = 0.001$). Additionally, differences in specific EI subscales were found to be statistically significant in relation to participants' age group and gender.

8 Qualitative Findings

8.1 Sample

The qualitative research sample consisted of 19 participants. The gender distribution shows relative balance, with a slight majority of men (52.4%), a trend that is uncommon in adult education research where women often predominate. However, the age composition reveals a clear concentration in the 40–59 age group (79%), consistent with the professional nature of the field. The high proportion of postgraduate degrees (63%) and the extensive professional experience of participants reflect a sample with a high level of specialization. Furthermore, the broad training in ICT and daily use by 68.4% of participants indicate familiarity with the digital environment. In contrast, the very limited certified training in EI (21.1%) and 5IR technologies (15.8%) highlights a significant educational

gap. Overall, the sample is considered sufficient for delving into interpretive issues of adult education but does not allow for the generalization of findings.

8.2 Qualitative Findings

The analysis of the interviews revealed strong convergence with the quantitative results, confirming the significance of EI in effective communication during adult education training. Participants repeatedly emphasized the contribution of empathy, self-regulation, and cultural sensitivity in educational practice, especially when interacting with heterogeneous groups. Technology was perceived as a useful but complementary tool, not replacing human relationships. Special emphasis was placed on the need for training not only in the use of digital tools but also in managing the emotional dynamics these tools evoke in the classroom. The lack of specialized training among educators in matters of EI and the 5IR was identified as a persistent weakness, making systematic professional development in these areas necessary. The qualitative data provide a rich interpretative background and contribute to the understanding of the statistical trends observed in the quantitative phase, thereby enhancing the validity of the study's conclusions.

9 Discussion – Comparison of Results

The analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data in the present study highlighted significant aspects of the role that EI plays

in the effective communication of adult educators, as well as its relationship with the technological challenges of the 5IR. The findings indicate a high level of skills in the domains of EI and Communication, with the highest mean score recorded in the subscale “Motivation” ($M = 4.37$), reflecting the strong motivation of participants to be actively involved in the learning process. However, lower scores were observed in “Empathy” ($M = 3.66$) and “Self-awareness” ($M = 3.67$), indicating relative weaknesses in understanding others’ emotions and internal self-awareness. The qualitative component corroborated these findings, as participants reported diverse practices aimed at enhancing empathy in practice, while simultaneously emphasizing the absence of structured training in the field of EI. The convergence of the two methodological approaches strengthens the validity of the conclusions, confirming the pivotal role of EI in educational practice and the need to reinforce it through targeted professional development. Regarding the correlation between EI and effective communication, the quantitative research revealed a very strong correlation ($r = 0.861$), supporting the view that these two domains are intrinsically linked in practice. Concurrently, educators in the interviews substantiated this relationship through examples of conflict management, collaborative learning, and empathetic interventions. The concept of cultural adaptability, which emerged primarily from the qualitative data, acts as an intermediary mechanism that enhances effective communication, especially in heterogeneous learning environments. Concerning the role

of digital technologies, participant attitudes showed variation. Quantitative scores for Digital Emotional Intelligence (DEI) were lower ($M = 3.13$), and its correlation with the other domains was limited. A similarly cautious attitude emerged in the qualitative data, with educators acknowledging the value of technologies but expressing concerns about artificial intelligence’s potential to replace human empathy. Technology is considered useful only when embedded within human-centered pedagogical frameworks, while the lack of training in this area was noted as a significant deficit. Finally, the challenges posed by 5IR were associated both with technological advances and with the psychological and pedagogical readiness of educators. Despite recognizing the potential of personalized learning and hybrid models, participants simultaneously underscored the necessity to preserve emotional authenticity and interpersonal relationships. Participants described feelings of fatigue, pressure, and ambivalence toward ongoing technological changes, which can be interpreted as indicators of a transformative challenge. Overall, the study revealed that strengthening EI, combined with targeted training in 5IR technologies, is a critical requirement to support adult educators in today’s reality. Comparatively, the findings of the present study align with previous research underscoring the importance of EI in supporting adult learners. Buvoltz et al. (2008) [BPSL08] identified a positive correlation between EI and learner’s autonomy. Gilar-Corbi et al. (2018) [GCPRSC18] demonstrated significant improvement in EI skills follow-

ing educational interventions. Cabello and Fernández-Berrocal (2015) [CFB15] emphasized the role of implicit theories in the development of EI and the necessity for educators to believe in their capacity to enhance their EI to achieve success. Motorga (2023) [Mot23] advocates the integration of EI techniques and coaching methods in adult education, particularly in the context of digital transition, highlighting the importance of guided empathy in empowering learners. These comparisons reinforce the findings of the present study and demonstrate that developing EI is not only feasible but essential within the framework of contemporary adult education.

10 Summary Answers to the Research Questions (RQ)

RQ1: Emotional Intelligence decisively influences communication effectiveness, with a strong correlation between the two variables ($r = 0.861$). Educators reporting high EI also rated their communicative competence positively. Qualitatively, EI was described as a critical tool for conflict management, cultural adaptation, and the development of empathetic interaction.

RQ2: Digital technologies can function supportively under specific conditions. Educators recognize the potential of digital environments to enhance engagement but emphasize the need for

specialized training and reflective use to cultivate emotional sensitivity.

RQ3: The main challenges identified include the lack of institutional training in EI, educator mental fatigue, and skepticism toward technology. Opportunities highlighted include maintaining emotional authenticity in the classroom, utilizing techniques such as dramatization and intercultural dialogue, and enabling personalized approaches supported by AI tools.

RQ4: The use of 5IR technologies is interpreted ambivalently. They can enhance EI when integrated into human-centered learning scenarios but may limit it when applied in a distancing manner. Participants acknowledged the need for ethical design, professional support, and continuous upgrading of educators' digital and emotional skills, so that technology acts as an ally rather than an obstacle to human communication.

11 Conclusions

This study explored the role of EI as a key factor for effective communication in adult education within the context of the 5IR. The findings reveal that EI is a decisive determinant for effective communication with a strong correlation. High scores on the "Motivation" subscale suggest that educators perceive themselves as active agents in emotional management, influence, and support of learners. However, relative weaknesses were identified in the sub-

Figure 3: Emotional Intelligence as a Factor of Effective Communication in 5IR

scales of Self-awareness and Empathy, indicating a need to strengthen the internal dimensions of EI through programs fostering self-reflection and awareness development. The analysis also highlighted ambivalence towards 5IR technologies. While most educators use digital tools daily, the lower scores on DEI point to a need for cultivating digital empathy and emotional presence in digital learning environments. Qualitative data showed that participants consider human interaction irreplaceable, even when acknowledging the usefulness of AI tools. The coexistence of technology and EI is interpreted as a dynamic balance requiring pedagogical design, ethical reflection and continuous training. Key challenges identified include the lack of institutional train-

ing in EI, skepticism towards new technologies, and educators' mental fatigue. Conversely, opportunities lie in the adoption of creative methods (e.g., dramatization, intercultural dialogue), fostering emotional authenticity in the classroom, and enabling personalized learning through AI. Overall, this study supports the view that EI constitutes a fundamental component of adult educators' professional competence, especially in an era of profound technological and social transformation. Future development in the field should focus on creating comprehensive training programs that integrate emotional and digital skills, aiming to promote a balanced, human-centered approach to education.

References

- [AAA25] L. Ayinde, A. O. Ajayi, and A. Adedeji. Reimagining the roles and skills of information professionals in the 5IR. *Business Information Review*, 42(1):10–19, 2025.
- [BC06] V. Braun and V. Clarke. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2):77–101, 2006.
- [BO06] R. Bar-On. The Bar-On model of emotional-social intelligence (ESI). *Psicothema*, 18:13–25, 2006.
- [BPSL08] K. A. Buvoltz, F. J. Powell, A. M. Solan, and G. J. Longbotham. Exploring emotional intelligence, learner autonomy, and retention in an accelerated undergraduate degree completion program. *New Horizons in Adult Education and Human Resource Development*, 22(3–4):26–43, 2008.
- [Bro17] S. D. Brookfield. *Becoming a critically reflective teacher*. Jossey-Bass., 2017.
- [BRS11] M. A. Brackett, S. E. Rivers, and P. Salovey. Emotional intelligence: Implications for personal, social, academic, and workplace success. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(1):88–103, 2011.
- [CB25] O. Cam and J. A. Ballantine. Exploring accounting academics’ views on sustainability: A Freirean dialogical pedagogic perspective. *The British Accounting Review*, 101633, 2025.
- [CFB15] R. Cabello and P. Fernández-Berrocal. Implicit theories and ability emotional intelligence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 6:700, 2015.
- [Col94] J. S. Coleman. *Foundations of social theory*. Harvard University Press, 1994.
- [Com21] European Commission. *Industry 5.0: Towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry*. <https://op.europa.eu>, 2021.
- [GCPRSC18] R. Gilar-Corbí, T. Pozo-Rico, B. Sánchez, and J. L. Castejón. Can emotional competence be taught in higher education. A randomized experimental study of an emotional intelligence training program using a multi-methodological approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9:1039, 2018.
- [Gol98] D. Goleman. *Working with emotional intelligence*. Bantam Books, 1998.

- [JG09] P. A. Jennings and M. T. Greenberg. Teacher social and emotional competence in relation to student and classroom outcomes. *Review of Educational Research*, 79(1):491–525, 2009.
- [JT04] P. J. Jordan and A. C. Troth. Managing emotions during team problem solving: Emotional intelligence and conflict resolution. *Human Performance*, 17(2):195–218, 2004.
- [Kas23] N. L. A. Kassim. 4ir, 5ir, society 5.0 and values in education. *IIUM Journal of Educational Studies*, 11(1):1–2, 2023.
- [KHIS14] M. S. Knowles, E. F. Holton III, and R. A. Swanson. The adult learner: The definitive classic in adult education and human resource development. *Routledge*, 2014.
- [KS20] T. J. Kennedy and C. W. Sundberg. 21st century skills. In *Science education in theory and practice: An introductory guide to learning theory*. Springer, pages 479–496, 2020.
- [LT06] J. P. Lantolf and S. L. Thorne. Sociocultural theory and the genesis of second language development. *Oxford University Press*, 2006.
- [MB18] S. B. Merriam and L. L. Bierema. Adult learning: Linking theory and practice. *Jossey-Bass*, 2018.
- [Mez00] J. Mezirow. Learning as transformation: Critical perspectives on a theory in progress. *Jossey-Bass*, 2000.
- [Mot23] M. E. Motorga. Digital transformation in adult education: empowering global understanding and sustainable development. *Revista de Științe ale Educației*, 48(2):46–63, 2023.
- [NMGP22] S. M. Noble, M. Mende, D. Grewal, and A. Parasuraman. The Fifth Industrial Revolution: How harmonious human–machine collaboration is triggering a retail and service [r]evolution. *Journal of Retailing*, 98(2):199–208, 2022.
- [PK18] G. Panagiotopoulos and Z. Karanikola. Contemporary working dilemmas and european policies for transformation. *Global Journal of Human Resource Management*, 6(3):1–10, 2018.
- [Sch24] K. Schwab. The fourth industrial revolution: what it means, how to respond. in *handbook of research on strategic leadership in the fourth industrial revolution*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pages 29–34, 2024.

- [SM90] P. Salovey and J. D. Mayer. Emotional intelligence. imagination. *Cognition and Personality*, 9(3):185–211, 1990.
- [TC13] E. W. Taylor and P. Cranton. A theory in progress? issues in transformative learning theory. *European journal for research on the education and learning of adults*, 4(1):33–47, 2013.
- [XDK18] M. Xu, J. M. David, and S. H. Kim. The fourth industrial revolution: Opportunities and challenges. *International journal of financial research*, 9(2):90–95, 2018.